

A Review on Properties and Pharmacological Activity of Naphthoquinone and its Derivatives

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Abstract

Naphthoquinone forms the central chemical structure of many natural compounds, most notably the K Vitamins. 2-Methylnaphthoquinone is a more effective coagulant than vitamin K. Naphthoquinone derivatives are cytotoxic, they have significant antibacterial, antifungal, antiviral, insecticidal, anti-inflammatory, and antipyretic properties. Quinone derivatives may be toxic to cells by a number of mechanisms including redox cycling, arylation, intercalation, induction of DNA strands breaks, generation of free radicals and alkylation via quinone methide formation. 5-Hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone, juglone, which is found in walnut hulls and leaves, is toxic and behaves as a weak tumor promoter in mouse skin. The bioactive quinones include lapachol, α -lapachone and β -lapachone, originally isolated from the heartwood of trees of the Bignoniaceae family (*Tabebuia* sp). The inner bark of *Tabebuia avellanedae*, commonly known as "pau d'arco" is used as an analgesic, an anti-inflammatory, an antineoplastic and a diuretic by the local people in the northeastern regions of Brazil. A series of synthetic isoxazolyl naphthoquinones was assayed in vitro and in vivo on *T. cruzi*, and the most active was (E)-4-(3,5-dimethylisoxazol-4-ylimino)-2-hydroxynaphthalene-1(4H)-one, which led to parasitemia reduction in infected mice. Plumbagin (5-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone) has been found to be active on epimastigote forms. Naphthoquinones are one of the groups of secondary metabolites widespread in nature. Catalysis of dioxygen reduction to hydrogen peroxide at the surface of carbon paste electrodes is modified by 1, 4-naphthoquinone and some of its derivatives.

Keywords: Naphthoquinone, Tumor, Antibacterial, Redox cycling

Introduction

Naphthoquinone is a class of organic compound derived from naphthalene. Three isomers are normally discussed: 1, 2-Naphthoquinone, 1, 4-Naphthoquinone, of which the Vitamin- K group compounds are derivatives 2,6-Naphthoquinone (amphi-naphthoquinone). *Lawsonia inermis* (Lythraceae) commonly known as, Henna is a shrub frequently cultivated in the Middle East, along the African coast of the Mediterranean Sea and India. Quinones, and particularly naphthoquinones (NQs) are widespread among the secondary metabolites of henna plant. Besides its use in cosmetics for staining hands and as a hair dye, the leaves are used as a prophylactic against skin diseases. It was reported to be useful in jaundice, enlargement of the spleen, calculus affliction, and skin diseases. (1) The extract of leaves of *L. inermis* has been shown to possess antimicrobial activity. (2) Ethanolic extract of the whole plant was found to have antifungal activity. (3) Quinones, and particularly naphthoquinones (NQs), are widespread among the

secondary metabolites of henna plant. The interest of naphthoquinones is not restricted to the chemistry of dyes; a wide spectrum of biological activities is described for them, including antitumor, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiparasitic, cytotoxic activities and others. (4,5,6) The biological activity of 1, 4-naphthoquinone is mainly due to the presence of two carbonyl groups that have the ability to accept one and/or two electrons to form the corresponding radical anion or di-anion species as well as their acid-base properties. (7)

In a recent study, it was found that the presence of hydroxy groups at 5 and 8 positions, which facilitate the tautomerism in the structure of 1, 4-naphthoquinone, should reduce the electrophilicity of the naphthoquinone ring. Thus the biological activity of naphthazarin (5, 8-dihydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone) derivatives is dependent upon the electrophilicity of the quinone moiety. Since, naphthazarin occurs in a resonance equilibrium state, so that its electron density will disperse over the ring. Thus the methylation of naphthazarin to produce 5, 8-dimethoxy-1,4-naphthoquinone (DMNQ) should increase the relative electrophilicity in C-2 and C-3 of the quinonoid moiety. This is evidenced by the greater reactivity of glutathione with DMNQ, compared with naphthazarin. (8)

Figure 1: Structure of Naphthoquinone

(Mono) hydroxynaphthoquinones

From 1, 4-naphthoquinone

Due to its symmetry there are only three isomers:

- 2-hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone (lawsone), coloring principle of henna.
- 5-Hydroxy-1, 4-naphthoquinone (juglone), coloring principle of black walnut. Also active antimicrobial principle in *Caesalpinia sappan* heartwood.
- 6-Hydroxy-1,4-naphthoquinone, can be prepared from 1,7-dihydroxynaphthalene. One of the main products of photochemical oxidation of 1-naphthol.

From 1, 2-naphthoquinone

From 1,2-naphthoquinone (ortho-naphthoquinone) there are 6 possible isomers:

- 3-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 4-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 5-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 6-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 7-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 8-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone

From 2, 3-naphthoquinone

From 2, 3-naphthoquinone, also a symmetric molecule there are only three isomers:

- 1-Hydroxy-2,3-naphthoquinone
- 5-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone
- 6-Hydroxy-1,2-naphthoquinone

From 2, 6-naphthoquinone

From the symmetrical 2,6-naphthoquinone (amphi-naphthoquinone) there are only three:

- 1-Hydroxy-2,6-naphthoquinone
- 3-Hydroxy-2,6-naphthoquinone
- 4-Hydroxy-2,6-naphthoquinone

(Poly) hydroxynaphthoquinones

- Dihydroxynaphthoquinone
- Trihydroxynaphthoquinone
- Tetrahydroxynaphthoquinone
- Pentahydroxynaphthoquinone
- Hexahydroxynaphthoquinone (9)

Mechanism of Action and Pharmacological Activity

The mechanism of their effect is highly large and complex however they bind to DNA and inhibit the processes, Replication, Interact with numerous proteins (enzymes) and Disturb cell and mitochondrial membranes; interfere with electrons of the respiratory chain on mitochondrial membranes. (10,11) There are numerous activities of naphthoquinone which are as follows:

1. Anti-cancer activity of Naphthoquinone:- Large number of naturally occurring 1, 2-naphthoquinones like rhinacanthone, beta lapachone, mansonones etc and synthetic 1, 2-naphthoquinones including prenyl 1,2-naphthohydroquinone, 1,2-naphthoquinonesemicarbazone, 1,2-furanonaphthoquinones and 1,2-pyranonaphthoquinones are found to have anticancer activity.

The cytotoxic effects of these quinines are mainly due to the following two factors:

A. Inhibition of DNA topoisomerase-II

B. Formation of semiquinone radical (12)

- 2, 3-Dichloro-5, 8-Dimethoxy-1, 4-Naphthoquinone is used as an Anti-breast Cancer Agent (13).
- Naphthoquinone derivatives have apoptotic effect on HCT116 colon cancer cells (14).

2. Anti viral activity of naphthoquinone derivatives:

Two new naphthoquinones, rhinacanthin-C (1) and rhinacanthin-D (2), exhibit inhibitory activity against cytomegalovirus (CMV) (15).

3. Anti-Infective Quinone Derivatives of Recent Patents:

Redox cycling is the concept in which compounds catalytically cycle and generate oxidative radicals, such as hydrogen peroxide and superoxide, which then damage the cell. Alkylation is when quinones are activated inside cells and become covalently attached to proteins, DNA, or other targets. The most important reaction of quinones as far as biology is concerned is their reversible reduction to the corresponding hydroquinone (Figure 2). (16)

Figure 2: Redox cycling of NADH or NAD(P)H and quinone.

4. Antimalarial activity of phenazines from lapachol, β -lapachone and its derivatives against *Plasmodium falciparum* in vitro and *Plasmodium berghei* in vivo (17)
5. Molluscicidal activity of 2-hydroxy-3-alkyl-1,4-naphthoquinones and derivatives (18)
6. Antibacterial Application: Naphthoquinone Derivatives are used in the Treatment and Control of Tuberculosis. Novel Furanonaphthoquinone Analogs also have antibacterial activity. (19)
7. Insecticidal activity of Naphthoquinone: Naphthoquinones have activities against *Aedes aegypti* (Diptera: Culicidae), vector of dengue and *Biomphalaria glabrata*, intermediate host of *Schistosoma mansoni*. (20)
8. The Trypanocidal Activity of Naphthoquinones: Naphthoquinone and derivatives have their importance in chagas disease which is caused by the protozoan *Trypanosoma cruzi*. The addition of β -lapachone to intact *T. cruzi* epimastigotes, or to mitochondrial or microsomal fractions, together with NADH or NADPH, induced the release of superoxide anion radical and H₂O₂ (21).
9. 2-methoxy-1,4-naphthoquinone and Stigmasta-7,22-diene-3 β -ol have in-vitro activity from *Impatiens balsamina* L. against Multiple Antibiotic-Resistant *Helicobacter pylori*. (22)
10. The role of Vitamin K in coagulation (23)

Secondary Metabolites Naphthoquinones

Table 1: Structural Formulas, Systematic and Trivial Names and Physical Properties of the Certain 1,4-naphthoquinones (24)

	Substituent	Systemic (Trivial) Name	Molecular Weight	Melting Point (°C)
	-	1,4 -Naphthoquinone	158.15	119 – 122
	$R_3 = -OH$	5-Hydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (juglone)	174.14	155
	$R_1 = -OH$	2-Hydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (lawsone)	174.15	192 – 195
	$R_1 = -CH_3, R_3 = -OH$	5-Hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-Naphthoquinone (plumbagin)	188.18	78 – 79
	$R_1 = -CH_3$	2-Methyl-1,4-Naphthoquinone (menadion)	172.18	105 – 107
	$R_3 = R_6 = -OH$	5,8-dihydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (naphthazalin)	190.16	237
	$R_1 = R_3 = R_5 = OH$	2,5,7-trihydroxy-1,4-Naphthoquinone (flaviolin)	206.17	164 – 168.5
	$R_1 = -CHOHCH_2$ $CH=C(CH_3)_2$ $R_3,$ $R_6 = -OH$	5,8-dihydroxy-2(1-hydroxy-4-methyl-pent-3-enyl)-1,4-Naphthoquinone (shikonin)	288.30	Not available
	$R_1 = -OH, R_2 = -$ $CH_2CH=C(CH_3)_2$	2-Hydroxy-3-(3-methyl-but-2-enyl)-1,4-Naphthoquinone (lapachol)	242.27	141 – 143

Properties of Naphthoquinone

- Catalysis of dioxygen reduction to hydrogen peroxide at the surface of carbon paste electrodes modified by 1, 4-naphthoquinone and some of its derivatives (25)
- Solid-phase extraction of metal ions and their estimation in vitamins, steel and milk using 3-hydroxy-2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone-immobilized silica gel (26)
- DT-diaphorase-catalysed reduction of 1,4-naphthoquinone derivatives and glutathionyl-quinone conjugates (27)
- Effect of ascorbate on the DT-diaphorase-mediated redox cycling of 2-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone (28)
- Effects of modulation of tissue activities of DT-diaphorase on the toxicity of 2,3-dimethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone to rats (29)
- Dual effects of superoxide dismutase on the autoxidation of 1,4-naphthoquinone (30)
- NAD(P)H:Quinone oxidoreductase activity is the principal determinant of beta-lapachone cytotoxicity (31)
- The roles of glutathione and antioxidant enzymes in menadione-induced oxidative stress (32)

The cytotoxicity of several quinonoid compounds can be understood as comprising three main mechanisms:

(a) autoxidation of the semiquinones or hydroquinones following the enzymic reduction of the oxidized counterparts and within a process of cycling characteristics yielding primarily.

(b) Addition reactions with cellular nucleophiles such as GSH, DNA, RNA and proteins.

(c) Inhibition of vital cellular functions such as DNA synthesis and mitochondrial electron transport.

The concerted participation of the above mechanisms can lead to modification of intracellular thiol balance and alteration of the intracellular Ca²⁺ homeostasis, and, eventually, cell death. Two processes can be envisaged in the reduction of quinones to either semiquinones or hydroquinones: on the one hand, the enzymic reduction of quinonoid compounds, and, on the other, the redox features of the addition chemistry of quinones. Firstly, quinones undergo one-electron reduction by a variety of flavoenzymes, including microsomal NADPH-cytochrome P-450 reductase, NADH-cytochrome b₅ reductase and mitochondrial NADH dehydrogenase, with concomitant formation of semiquinone species. DT-diaphorase [NAD(P)H: quinone oxidoreductase, an enzyme present in most animal tissues, catalyses formally the two-electron reduction of quinones to hydroquinones. (33)

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